

A Study of EFL Classroom Management at the Higher Secondary Level in Bangladesh

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Abstract:- This study conducts on the topic "A Study of EFL Classroom Management at the Higher Secondary Level" to determine the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement. The objectives are to: (a) determine the level of effectiveness of classroom management, (b) establish the level of learners' achievement, and (c) form the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level. The study adopts a quantitative paradigm with a cross-sectional correlation survey design and a sample of 35 respondents who participate in the study. A self-administered closed-ended Likert-type (5-point scale) instrument is used to collect quantitative data through a questionnaire survey method, which is analyzed manually. The level of classroom management and level of learners' achievement is tested manually, and the test results indicate a significantly low level of classroom management and noticeably low level of learners' achievement at the higher secondary level. The study finds a significant positive relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement, while the effect of predictor variables on learners' achievement is determined using multiple regression analysis, implying that it is a significant predictor of learners' achievement. The researcher, therefore, recommends that Principals and teachers may use the findings to improve classroom management practices for better learning achievement.

Keywords:- Principle, Procedure, Achievement, Classroom management, Responsibility.

I. INTRODUCTION

Classroom management is a crucial factor of the total education system; although there are some problems with classroom management in many academic subjects, those are the critical area of research in general education in many countries (Doyle, 1990; Jones, 1996; Kagan, 1994; Tauber, 1997). Compared to the level of interest in general education, more attention should be paid to classroom management issues in language classrooms. In particular, there is little empirical research on classroom management in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in Bangladesh. This study will report on: a) classroom management difficulties that arise in Bangladeshi EFL classrooms when teachers teach English communicatively, b) how teachers conceptualize and attempt to deal with these problems, and c) what strategies can be offered to alleviate these problems.

➤ Background of the Study

The research subject is essential because classroom management (CM) is vital for every teacher. Student English teachers (ST) report experiencing a handful of problems related to CM (Merç, 2004). According to Luo et. al. (2000), controlling classroom environments can be overwhelming for many graduate teaching assistants. Even teachers with 25 years of experience can face CM problems (Kyriacou, 1991). When the component of a foreign language classroom is added to the setting, the situation becomes even more problematic and uncertain (Fowler & Şaraplı, 2010). Teachers from all over the world are employing several techniques to deal with the possible forthcoming CM problems. Whether these strategies work well for their classrooms or fail is the research area for teacher education researchers (Altınel, 2006; Baker & Westrup, 2000; Tahir & Qadir, 2012). For building an effective training model, there is an urgent need to examine the CM issues in depth and identify ST management techniques that are best suited for effective language teaching. Therefore, this study will show an attempt to provide insights into the pedagogical strategies ST employs to plan, organize, and motivate student learning. Today's STs are likely to become tomorrow's professionals. An inquiry into helping ST become effective classroom managers will benefit their students and language teaching methodology courses provided in faculties of education. Furthermore, although it has found its place in teacher education research and language teaching methodologies, there has been little research to investigate the CM problems STs face while delivering lessons. Therefore, this study is a promising one to explain and interpret the possible specific problems of ST related to CM and their coping techniques.

➤ Objectives of the Study

This study is focused on the following objectives:

- To identify steps for planning a classroom management concept.
- To determine the level of effectiveness of classroom management at the higher secondary level.
- To establish the level of learners' achievement at the higher secondary level.
- To establish the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level.

➤ *Justification of the Study*

This study will provide reliable information to policymakers in the Ministry of Education, college owners, and college management teams who might use it in reviewing education-related policies. The study report shall enable the various practitioners within the college settings, including the principals, teachers, and students, to further their understanding of classroom management requirements and improve on the classroom management gaps. This research report will further help other scholars, researchers, and research users by providing literature and methodological guidance to build on further research, especially in areas related to classroom management at higher secondary schools.

➤ *Research Hypothesis*

- What is the level of effectiveness of classroom management at the higher secondary level?
- What is the level of learners' achievement at the higher secondary level?
- What is the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level?

➤ *Limitations of the Study*

Although this research is carefully prepared, the researcher is still aware of its limitations and shortcomings.

First, the research is conducted in the seven higher secondary institutions, which is needed for the researcher to observe all of the institutions. It would be better if it would do most of the institutions in Dhaka City.

Second, the population of the experimental group is small, with only twenty-eight teachers and seven principals, and might not represent the majority of the teachers and principals. Third, since the questionnaires designed to measure the teachers' attitude toward using EFL classroom management strategies may give helpful information about the impacts, more evidence is needed of the teachers' actual EFL classroom management performance.

II. CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

➤ *Classroom Management*

Classroom management is the "actions taken to create and maintain a learning environment conducive to successful instruction" (Brophy, 1996, p. 5). It is also thought to integrate four areas: "establishing and reinforcing rules and procedures, carrying out disciplinary actions, maintaining effective teacher and student relationships, and maintaining an appropriate mental set for management" (Marzano & Marzano, 2003, p. 88). Classroom management should not be seen as synonymous with classroom discipline; it involves those other aspects mentioned above that are equally inherent to teaching. Crooks (2003) similarly sees a well-managed classroom as a relatively orderly room in which "whatever superficial manifestations of disorder that may occur either do not prevent instruction and learning or support them" (p. 144). The above

definitions of classroom management have established an appropriate environment and order in the classroom so that teaching and, subsequently, learning can take place. A well-managed classroom can play an essential role in building a good society, nation, or a good man who will be the maker of society and nation. For this reason, a teacher is called a manager.

➤ *Background to the Study*

Traditional classroom management practices have been centered on an educational curriculum for the last three centuries emphasizing teacher-centeredness, discipline, and one-directional transmission of knowledge to learners (Claassen & Marbach-Ad, 1998). However, according to Johnson & Johnson (1999), the trend in classroom management follows early thinking about children who are seen as idle and undisciplined creatures needing mental and physical training. Studies conducted during the 20th Century in different countries indicate a list of personal characteristics of successful teachers in classroom management (Gordana & Snezana, 2011) which includes warmth, kindness, friendliness, democratic attitudes, cooperativeness, consistency, openness of thought, and broad interests that are believed to impact positively on learners. Classroom management is therefore considered an issue dealing with students' behavior. Classroom management poses more significant challenges today than it was in the past when the traditional approach of reward(s) and punishment(s) was common in African schools (Scott, 1996). The present classroom management is geared towards realizing learning achievement (Kraus, 2016), and this is why teachers employ strategies like extra written work, removal of privileges, suspension from class, and community services to stubborn learners.

According to Skinner's Operant Conditioning of Learning (1961), positive and negative reinforcement influences voluntary behavior. It implies that teachers who use positive reinforcement on the learner, that is, "if the learner does something pleasant", that learner receives a reward, and teachers who use negative reinforcement on the learner, that is, "if the learner does something good", then the unpleasant experience is removed from that learner. Skinner (1961) believes both conditions boost achievement, and it is ultimately up to the teacher and the prevailing situation to choose what outcome will work best to improve the learner's behavior and ensure the class can run as an efficient learning environment. The best way to understand behavior is to look at the causes of an action and its consequences (Skinner, 1961). From Skinner's positive reinforcement theory, Jones & Jones (2016) developed a non-adversarial model of creating a classroom that moves smoothly. In that, he came up with the three steps that include the positive practices, how the class can achieve from the positive practices, and taking notes of every day and every minute problem the teacher faces. It, he said, can lead to learners' achievement. According to Kraus (2016), classroom management refers to the teacher's ability to plan, organize and control students' behaviors. The actions and strategies are used to maintain order in the classroom (Burden, 2000). This author defines classroom management

as the ability of the teacher to prepare, present, control, and manage the class record in a manner that leads to learners' achievement.

Although Burden (2000) suggests that learners' achievement is also paramount, he defines it as; meeting students' needs to obtain success and avoid failure. It is accomplished especially by exertion, skill, Practice, or perseverance. However, Stephen (2007) defines learners' achievement as the ability of a student to excel in academics, possess essential life skills, and have a sense of responsibility to contribute to society. In this study, learners' achievement is defined as the positive practices the learner has adapted and succeeded in doing. These practices include getting a good grade, time management, positive behavior change, class participation, attendance, smartness, and paying attention in class. However, learners in Bangladesh are accused of not observing class rules, negatively impacting their achievement. Research conducted in the United States of America (USA) finds that the teacher as a classroom manager is a broker of contradictory interests, one who "builds a working identity that is constructively ambiguous (Magdalene, 2011)." To emphasize her conviction that teaching work is deeply personal, the author makes herself the subject of one of those studies. She concludes with an examination of how her view contrasts with prevalent academic images of teachers' work. However, studies conducted in the United Kingdom have shown that teacher aggressive classroom management scares students from learning (Patton, 1990). Learning achievement is high in the classroom with fewer disciplinary problems since teachers have to spend more time creating an orderly environment before instruction can begin (PISA, 2011). Interruptions in the classroom disrupt students' concentration and engagement in their lessons and, consequently, achievement.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

Classroom management is one of the critical components of any educational achievement. Higher Secondary schools achieve this due to teacher-classroom management ability and student compliance with classroom norms (Smith, 2009). According to the lesson assessment instrument of Gulu University Faculty of Education and Humanities, effective classroom management depends on the teacher's ability to prepare effectively, present the content consistently, control learners' behavior, and maintain class records. At the same time, the learner, on the other hand, is expected to comply with the class's rules and follow guidance from the teacher. Consequently, the learner will be able to get a good grades in exams, manage time effectively, portray positive behavior practices, participate actively in class, and maintain general smartness.

Classroom observation conducted by the Ministry of Education reveals that there needs to be more preparation scheme-of-work, lesson plans, and content coverage among teachers in higher secondary schools in Bangladesh. The report further exposes teacher-centered teaching, poor learning environment, and disorderliness in the classrooms is observed. It is believed to have resulted in non-

compliance by learners who disrupt lessons, ignore assignments, have low concentration and participation in class activities, sleep in class and criticize teachers. It may be contrary to Jones & Jones (2012), who said that: "Teacher-good practices in the teaching-learning process attract corporation from the class hence learners' achievement." arising from the desirable situation highlighted above, this study is to answer the question of whether classroom management enhances learners' achievement in higher secondary schools in Bangladesh.

➤ *Methodology*

The study population is 49. It includes all teachers and principals of studies in the seven higher secondary schools (colleges) in Dhaka City. Teachers are selected because they are directly concerned with classroom management, and principals of studies are mainly responsible for supervising teaching and monitoring class progress. According to Amin (2005), a representative sample gives results that can be generalized to the study population. The sample of seven colleges and thirty-five (35) respondents are selected from all categories of teaching staff and principals of study. The sample size determination is based on Watson, M. (2006) table for sample size determination. According to this table, there are given sample size(s) for the population. The researcher's target population is 49 respondents, including twenty-five teachers and seven principals of study, from seven selected higher secondary schools in Dhaka City. This sample is representative, and the researcher is confident of the study's generalization.

The researcher uses a questionnaire survey method for collecting data from respondents because the population is large and literate, and the information required is simple and easy to fill in the responses. This method can collect information quickly (Amin, 2005). The study employs a self-administered closed-ended questionnaire to collect data from teachers and principals of the study. Macmillan and Schumacher (2001) recommend a questionnaire if the researcher knows that the respondents will be able to answer the questionnaire. Closed-ended and scaled items are used. According to Macmillan and Schumacher (2001), the scaled items allow fairly accurate opinions assessments.

Similarly, it could solicit information from several respondents within a limited time. The quantitative data is processed, entered, and analyzed manually. The effectiveness of classroom management and the level of learners' achievement is determined. In this test, the determinant of the levels is based on the degree of variation of the responses from the expected value. For example, "Pearson product-moment correlation" determines the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement. In contrast, "multiple regression analysis" is used to determine which of the variables of classroom management is the better predictor of learners' achievement at the higher secondary schools in Dhaka City.

The following categories illustrate the main findings of the study: Classroom Management affects teaching regardless of subject or experience. Some participants, particularly EFL teachers at higher secondary schools, claim that the classroom management issues teachers encounter in the practicum are inevitably part of the teaching profession and not exclusive to language teaching. However, they know that it is something teachers have to confront and learn along the way, regardless of the subject they have to teach.

➤ *Challenges and Factors that Affect Classroom Management*

Regarding specific classroom management challenges that EFL teachers encounter in their practicum, many such challenges have to do with external, nonacademic factors that influence students' behavior or do not contribute to a good learning atmosphere in the context of secondary and higher secondary schools. One such factor is the high temperatures in class because the weather in the city is usually sweltering, and the classrooms are not equipped with air conditioning or ceiling fans. Noise from outside is another factor usually caused by different sources (people on the street, students in other classrooms, and cultural and social activities inside the school).

➤ *Approaches to Managing the Classroom*

Regarding teachers' approaches to managing their classrooms, responses vary depending on the problem or situation. However, maintaining control is the most predominant approach among teachers across school settings. Most participants, including teachers and principals, claim that teachers make great efforts to control students' behavior in a class by establishing and reinforcing strict rules from the beginning and reminding students of the harsh consequences if they do not follow them. This approach typically involves talking louder to the students to regain their attention, writing notes in their notebooks so that their parents can see them, reminding students of who is in charge, intimidating students with negative remarks or low grades, assigning extra work in class to keep them busy, and at times getting into verbal confrontations with students.

➤ *Improving Classroom Management*

The EFL teacher education program could help teachers improve their classroom management skills; participants in both settings emphasize that the program should offer them more opportunities to be involved in authentic school settings. However, most teachers claim this can be achieved through different strategies, such as a course on classroom management with both theoretical and practical components and more specific observation.

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

According to Skinner's Operant Conditioning of Learning (1961), positive and negative reinforcement influences voluntary behavior. It implies that teachers who use positive reinforcement on the learner, that is, "if the learner does something pleasant," that learner receives a reward, and teachers who use negative reinforcement on the learner, that is, "if the learner does something good," then the unpleasant experience is removed from that learner.

Skinner believes both conditions boost achievement, and it is ultimately up to the teacher and the prevailing situation to choose what outcome will work best to improve the learner's behavior and ensure the class can run as an efficient learning environment. The best way to understand behavior is to look at the causes of an action and its consequences (Skinner, 1961).

From Skinner's positive reinforcement theory, Jones & Jones (2012) developed a non-adversarial model of creating a classroom that moves smoothly. In that, he comes up with the three steps that include the positive practices, how the class can achieve from the positive practices, and taking notes of every day and every minute problem the teacher faces. It, he said, can lead to learners' achievement. According to Kraus (2016), classroom management refers to the teacher's ability to plan, organize and control students' behaviors. The actions and strategies are used to maintain order in the classroom (Burden, 2000). This author defines classroom management as the ability of the teacher to prepare, present, control, and manage the class record in a manner that leads to learners' achievement.

The framework shows the relationship between Independent Variable, classroom management, and the Dependent Variable, learners' achievement affected by the intervening variables. There is an assumed linkage between classroom management indicators (i.e., lesson preparation, lesson presentation, class control, and record management) and learners' achievement indicators, namely; getting a good grade, time management, understanding concepts, regular attendance, smartness, being attentive during the lesson, and handing in assignments. The implication is that; good classroom management enhances learners' achievement. Therefore, if teachers manage their classes well, then learners are more likely to achieve higher academically. According to the Operant Conditioning Theory of Skinner (1961), classroom management indicators cause behavior problems that need to be addressed to realize learners' achievement. The framework also shows that the intervening variable indicators (teacher qualification, age of teacher and learner, gender of the teacher and the learner, experience of the teacher, learners' background, and learners' attitudes) affect the relationship between the independent and the dependent variables implying that when well controlled, learners' achievement is realized. This study can help the learners know their achievement levels as a class and adjust to classroom requirements for better learning. They can, therefore, pay attention in class, comply with classroom rules and perform all tasks assigned to them by the teacher.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher presents in this chapter the sampling, research design, study population, sampling procedure, data collection techniques, instrument, quality control, research administration procedure, ethical considerations, and data analysis.

➤ *Sampling*

According to Amin (2005), a representative sample gives results that can be generalized to the study population. The sample of seven colleges and 42 respondents were selected from teachers and principals of the study. The sample size was determined based on Watson & Battistich's (2006) table for sample size determination. According to this table, there are given sample size(s) for the population. The researcher's target population is 42 respondents comprising 35 teachers and seven principals of study at higher secondary schools in Dhaka City. This sample is believed to be representative, and the researcher is confident of the generalizability of the study.

Table 1 Sampling Frame

S/n	Categories of respondents	Total populations	Sample size
1	Colleges	7	7
2	Principals	7	7
3	Teachers	35	28
	Total	49	42

Fig 1 Sample Size, Primary Data

➤ *Colleges*

In selecting colleges, the researcher uses simple random sampling, particularly the lottery method, where the names of colleges are written on a piece of paper, folded, and picked randomly by the research assistants. The first seven colleges are picked from the sample. This method is the simplest to use and has no bias.

➤ *Classroom Teachers*

Classroom Teachers are selected using simple continuous sampling from the attendance register booklets. Simple random sampling is a method employed to select a sample without bias from the target population (Amin, 2005).

➤ *Principals*

Principals are selected using purposive sampling, while teachers and students are selected using simple random sampling from the attendance register booklets. In this method, each member of the population has an equal chance to be included in the study, and its advantage is that a representative sample will be used to reflect the view of the entire population (Amin, 2005).

➤ *Instruments*

The study employs a self-administered closed-ended questionnaire to collect data from teachers and principals of the study. Macmillan and Schumacher (2001) recommend a questionnaire if the researcher knows that the respondents will be able to answer the questionnaire. Closed-ended and scaled items are used. According to Macmillan and Schumacher (2001), the scaled items allow fairly accurate opinions assessments. Similarly, it can solicit information from several respondents within a short time.

➤ *Questionnaire*

Here the researcher-controlled quality by establishing the validity and reliability of the questionnaire.

➤ *Validity*

The validity of research instruments is assured by assessing the questionnaire items during construction. Validity is when the tool used to collect data corresponds with the variables in the study to produce accurate results (Amin, 2005). Questions are discussed with the supervisor, who provides technical input before administering them to the respondents. It is to clear any lack of clarity and ambiguity. The relevance of the questions where measures with the objectives of the study and scores against the classroom observation tool. The content validity index is computed as below:

- Content Validity Index (CVI) = $\frac{\text{Number of items rated relevant}}{\text{Total number items in the questionnaire}}$
- $CVI = \frac{21}{25}$
- $CVI = 0.84$

It is supported by Amin (2005), who states that for any instrument to be accepted as valid, the average index should be 0.70 and above.

➤ *Reliability*

Reliability is the extent to which a test or procedure of data collection yields similar results under constant conditions on all occasions (Amin, 2005). The reliability of the questionnaire is ensured by pre-testing. The researcher gives questionnaires to the teachers and principals at the higher secondary level, different from the sampled schools in Dhaka City, for pre-testing. The test result is analyzed manually, confirming that the instrument is reliable since each variable has an item-scale correlation.

➤ *Data Collection*

The data is collected from different higher secondary schools, which the investigator selects randomly. Next, he collects the institution name, sets it in alphabetical order, and collects the selected name.

➤ *Data Analysis*

The quantitative data is processed, entered, and analyzed manually. The effectiveness of classroom management and the level of learners' achievement is determined. In this test, the determinant of the levels is based on the degree of variation of the responses from the

expected value. For example, "Pearson product-moment correlation" determines the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement. In contrast, "multiple regression analysis" is used to determine which of the variables of classroom management is the better predictor of learners' achievement at higher secondary schools in Dhaka City.

IV. FINDINGS

This chapter presented analyses and interprets the characteristics of respondents, the level of effectiveness of classroom management (lesson preparation, lesson presentation, class control, and record management), the level of learners' achievement, and the effect of classroom

management on learners' achievement at the higher secondary schools in Dhaka City. All presentations are made in tables and figures and analyzed according to research questions.

➤ Respondents' Characteristics

The information about the background characteristics of respondents at the higher secondary schools in Dhaka City has been presented in this section. The study is conducted among 42 respondents from 7 higher secondary schools (colleges) in Dhaka City. The variables presented in table 2 include the category of respondents, sex, and age. The qualification and experience of teachers and directors of study are also included in the table.

Table 2 Background Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Valid percentage
Respondents	Principals	7	20%
	Teachers	28	80%
Sex	Males	22	83%
	Females	13	17%
Age	29-34	19	54%
	35-40	7	20%
	41-45	2	6%
	Above 45	7	20%
Qualifications of Teachers and Principals	Masters Degree	35	100%
	PhD	0	0%
Experience of teachers and Principals	Below three years	7	20%
	3-5 years	10	29%
	6-9 years	6	17%
	Above 10	12	34%

Source: Field Data

Table 2 above shows that the majority of respondents are teachers (80%) and Principals (20%), implying that the majority of respondents were teachers (80%). The table also shows that most respondents were males (83%) followed by females (17%), implying that there were more males than females in the study, which suggests the enrolment in terms of gender. The table also shows that the majority of respondents (54%) are in the age range of 29-30, followed by 35-40 years (20%), then those at the age of 41-45(6%), and lastly those aged above 45 (20%). It implies that most of the respondents, 29-30 years (54%), are more likely to be teachers, followed by 29-35 years (80%), who are more likely to be principals. The table further reveals the qualification of teachers and principals of study being the same (100%). Finally, it reveals the experiences of teachers and Principals of Study, with 34% having served above ten years and 29% below three to five years. It implies that most respondents have more than ten years of experience in the service.

➤ Research Question One

What is the effectiveness of EFL classroom management at the higher secondary level? Respondents are given four (4) areas to measure to determine the effectiveness of classroom management. These include teacher preparation, lesson presentation, class control, and record management. The ratings are based on the Likert scale (1932), and the results are presented in tables.

Table 3 Level of the Effectiveness of Teacher Preparation

Teacher Preparation		Response				
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Some teachers use notes book only when teaching	6%	85%	0%	6%	3%
2	The classroom is congested and does not allow easy movement	18%	45%	23%	7%	7%
3	Some teachers use textbooks only when teaching	34%	60%	6%	3%	0%
4	Students are not comfortable with sitting arrangements in the classroom	18%	36%	28%	7%	11%

Source: Field Data

Table 3 shows that the majority of respondents 85% agree that some teachers use only lesson notes books when teaching, 45% agree that the classroom is congested, 60% agree that some teachers use textbooks only when teaching and do not allow easy movement while 36% agree that they are not comfortable with sitting arrangements in the classroom. The percentage response scores on the level of elements of lesson presentation at the higher secondary level are presented in table 4.

Table 4 Level of the Effectiveness of Lesson Presentation

Lesson Presentation		Response				
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Some teachers start teaching without reviewing the previous lesson	34%	37%	23%	0%	6%
2	Some teachers do not have full Knowledge of the Content being taught	14%	31%	28%	20%	6%
3	Some teachers' voices in not clear while teaching	17%	43%	14%	14%	11%
4	Some students are not actively involved in participating in the class	34%	31%	17%	6%	11%
5	Some teachers' handwriting is not clear on the blackboard	17%	54%	11%	3%	14%
6	The teachers always handle Learner's Contributions positively	23%	43%	20%	9%	6%
7	Students always do not like the lesson being taught	14%	57%	14%	14%	0%
8	Some teachers do not assess learners during lesson conduction	26%	34%	26%	3%	11%
9	Some teachers only copy notes with less explanation	34%	31%	14%	9%	11%
10	Some teachers do not share lesson objectives with learners in the class	29%	57%	0%	14%	0%

Source: Field Data

According to table 4 above, 37% of respondents agree that some teachers start teaching without reviewing the previous lesson, 57% agree that some teachers do not share lesson objectives with learners, and 31% agree that some teachers need complete knowledge of what they teach. The table further shows that 43% of respondents agree that some teachers' voices could be more unmistakable while teaching, 34% strongly agree that some students are not actively participating in class activities, and 54% agree that some teachers' handwriting needs to be clarified. It is also revealed in the table that 57% of respondents agree that students always do not like the lesson being taught, 43% agree that the teacher always does not handle learners' contribution positively, 34% agree that some teachers do not assess learners during the lesson and finally, 34% strongly agree that some teachers only copy notes with less explanation.

- The presentation of the percentage scores of responses on the elements of class control at the higher secondary level is in table 5.

Table 5 Level of the Effectiveness of Class Control

Class Control		Response				
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Some students disturb others during lessons and discussion	20%	43%	9%	17%	11%
2	There are unnecessary movements by some learners during learning	21%	29%	25%	14%	11%
3	Some teachers do not attend to the individual learner during teaching	14%	58%	14%	7%	7%
4	The teacher does not supervise group activities	23%	23%	23%	11%	20%
5	Some teachers are not competent and presentable in the class	43%	29%	14%	14%	0%
6	Some teachers report late to class	43%	57%	0%	0%	0%
7	There are no rules specifically for the classroom that they have seen	29%	29%	18%	14%	11%

Source: Field Data

The study result in table 5 shows that 29% strongly agree and 29% agree that there is no rule specifically for the class that they have ever seen, 43% agree that some students disturb others during lessons and discussions, 29% agree that there are unnecessary movements by learners during a lesson and 58% agree that some teachers do not attend to individual learners during a lesson. The table further shows that 23% strongly agree and 23% agree that the teacher does not supervise class activities, 43% strongly agree that some teachers are not intelligent and presentable in the classroom, and 57% agree that some teachers consistently report late to the classroom.

- Figure 2 gives the percentage response distribution on the elements of record management at the higher secondary level.

Fig 2 Level of the Effectiveness of Record Management, Field Data

According to figure 2 above, 46% agree that teachers do not make roll calls daily, and 43% agree that the class teacher does not properly keep records of assessment scores. All the elements of classroom management measured have a significantly low level of effectiveness since the distribution of responses in support of a low level is above the expected value that would determine the equal distribution of responses in all the categories. It is an indication that there needs to be a significantly higher level of effectiveness of classroom management at the higher secondary level in Dhaka City.

➤ *Research Question Two*

The question “What is the level of EFL learners’ achievement at the higher secondary level?” Findings of all the elements of learners’ achievement are presented in figure 3 and analyzed.

Fig 3 Level of Learners’ Achievement, Field Data

According to figure 3 above, 57% of respondents agree that students do not get very high marks on tests and exams, 25% agree that some students come late to class, and 46% agree that some do not attend lessons. The table also reveals that 29% agree that some students sleep in class sometimes, 54% agree that some students talk during a lesson, and 36% agree that some students do not turn in assignments for marking. All the elements of classroom management measured had a significantly low level of effectiveness since the distribution of responses in support of a low level is above the expected value that would determine the equal distribution of responses in all the categories. In addition, it indicates a significantly low level of learners' achievement at the higher secondary level in Dhaka City.

➤ *Research Question Three*

The question states, "What is the relationship between EFL classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level?"

The researcher uses Pearson correlation statistics to measure the "relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement" and to determine the hypothesis that: "There is no significant relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level." The relationships of all four elements of classroom management (i.e., lesson preparation, lesson presentation, class control, and record management) have been measured against learners' achievement. Multiple regression analysis has been used to determine learner achievement predictor variables. All the variables except teacher preparation are significant predictors of learners' achievement at a 5% significance level.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions are made in line with the study objectives supported by the analyzed data. It includes (1) the level of classroom management, (2) the level of learners' achievement, and (3) the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level in Dhaka City. The study reveals a low level of classroom management at the higher secondary level, and teachers' ineffectiveness in planning, employing teaching methodologies, class control, and record management is very high. The finding further reveals a deficient level of learners' achievement, characterized by low academic performance in tests and examinations, poor time management, lack of attention during lesson conduction, and poor class hygiene management. Finally, the finding reveals a significant positive relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level.

The findings of this study can help college administrators, teachers, and students understand classroom management factors and how they affect learning achievement. Principals should use the findings from this study to devise practical supervision approaches to the teaching and learning process, set achievement targets for individual classes, and provide capacity development

training for teachers in classroom management. Teachers should be able to revisit how they manage their classrooms using the findings of this study. They should, therefore, be able to effectively plan, teach and evaluate the performance of their learners based on the pre-set achievement goal(s). Engagement of learners in classroom management practices such as setting self-goals and class rules will motivate learners to own what they have made and implement it accordingly. Finally, this study can help the learners know their achievement levels as a class and adjust to classroom requirements for better learning. They can, therefore, pay attention in class, comply with classroom rules and perform all tasks assigned to them by the teacher.

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